

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

THE CONNECTION BETWEEN DEBRIEFING AND A CULTURE OF SAFETY IN
THE OPERATING ROOM

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Rita K. Thompson

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Glenn Raup PhD, MSN, MBA, RN, CEN, Project Chair
Darlene Finnochiaro, PhD, RN, CRRN, PN, Committee Member

May 2019

Copyright Rita K. Thompson ©

ABSTRACT

Staff perception of the culture of safety in addition to other barriers were identified as potential contributors to inconsistent performance of debriefing procedures at a Southern California medical center hospital, 12-suite, surgical department. The Joint Commission (TJC) has identified ineffective communication as a critical contributor to events related to patient safety regarding healthcare. Evidence shows a standardized process for debriefing based on staff input can improve the commitment to performing debriefings. This quality improvement project aimed to improve the consistency in use of the debriefing process in the operating room (OR) through assessments of barriers, the perceptions of what constitutes a culture of safety, and proposed revisions to the standardized process to performance of debriefings in order to improve consistency and accuracy. The surgical safety checklist (SSC) is a tool to assist with decreasing errors and improving teamwork and communication in the OR and procedural areas. The debriefing process is an essential element of the SSC that contributes to a culture of effective communication and patient safety. There is evidence to support that when the debriefing process is integrated properly such as use as part of the SSC, it contributes to a culture of effective communication which in turn has been shown to be a vital part of an OR culture where patient safety is understood and a top priority (Donnelly, 2017).

In this quality improvement project, forty-two (42) of the total 81 (52%) staff at the medical center participated in voluntary completion of survey assessments selected to

identify their perceptions of what makes a culture of safety and confidence around performing debriefings. Demographic practice and role related data was also collected which revealed an experienced staff with 61.7% having 11 or more years of experience in the OR setting. Key results from a modified version of the Safety Assessment Questionnaire (SAQ) revealed only 45.24% of the staff “strongly agreed” that debriefings were a common practice currently in the OR while the remaining 55.76% of responses ranged from ‘strongly disagree’ to ‘slightly agree’. Additionally, responses to all five of the questions in the validated tool known as the Confidence Scale (Grundy, 1993) ranged from 44.19 to 63.64% of the time in which staff indicated they were not absolutely certain they were performing the debriefing process correctly or efficiently. Assessment tool results indicated that identification of cultural and care process barriers and facilitators related to safety prior to implementation of the current debriefing process had not occurred which was validated by staff’s lack of awareness of the link between inconsistent and inaccurate performance in the debriefing process and its relationship to their perception of a culture of safety.

Based on the findings, recommendations were made to the leadership at the hospital to focus on revising the organization’s reporting methods for adverse events by staff so as to include awareness of the link between reporting and a “true” culture of safety. Additionally, greater examination of the organizational culture of safety specifically, why staff felt they did not have the confidence to consistently perform the debriefing, is recommended before implementing any changes to the current debriefing process in order to ensure greater success with the change process.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
BACKGROUND	1
Overview.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	3
Supporting Framework	3
Iowa Model of Evidence Based Practice	4
Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change.....	6
LITERATURE REVIEW	10
Search Methods & Results.....	10
Overview.....	11
Debriefing in the OR.....	11
Teamwork and Team Dynamics	12
Communication.....	13
Barriers to Communication and Debriefing.....	13
Proposed Solutions	14
Summary of Literature.....	15
METHODS	16
Design	16
Ethical Considerations	17
Sample and Setting	18
Instruments.....	18
Safety Attitudes Questionnaire (Modified).....	19
The Confidence Scale	19
Organizational Readiness for Intent to Change (Modified).....	19
Data Collection & Intervention.....	20

RESULTS	21
Findings	21
Evaluation	24
DISCUSSION	25
SUMMARY	28
REFERENCES	29
APPENDIX A: MODIFIED SAFETY ATTITUDES QUESTIONNAIRE	36
APPENDIX B: THE CONFIDENCE SCALE	39
APPENDIX C: MODIFIED ORGANIZATIONAL READINESS FOR INTENT TO CHANGE.....	40
APPENDIX D: PERMISSION TO USE THE IOWA MODEL (2015).....	41
APPENDIX E: PERMISSION TO USE SAFETY ATTITUDES QUESTIONNAIRE	42
APPENDIX F: PERMISSION TO USE THE CONFIDENCE SCALE.....	43
APPENDIX G: PERMISSION TO USE ORGANIZATIONAL READINESS FOR INTENT TO CHANGE	45
APPENDIX H: TABLE OF EVIDENCE	47

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Modified SAQ and Demographics of the Medical Center OR Staff.....	21
2. C-Scale Practice Counts and Frequencies	23

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Iowa Model	8
2. Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change	9

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank my parents, Dale and Dolores Toth, for their endless support in all I choose to do. Thank you, Mom for teaching me I could be anything I worked for. Thank you, Dad, for instilling in me the importance of education. To my sons, Nicholas and Stanton, my pride and joy, thank you for encouraging me in all my wild ideas, teaching me how to be a better person, and keeping me humble. To my family and friends who encouraged me on my quest for this degree, including the new friends I made in this program, I would like to thank you as your support was more valued than you may know.

I would like to acknowledge and thank Dr. Glenn Raup for his tireless help, guidance, and support in my project, Dr. Finnochiaro for her support, and Dr. Rutledge for pushing me to be a better writer. I would like to thank all the professors and administrators of the Southern California State University Doctor of Nursing Practice Consortium program for the support and encouragement throughout the program.

BACKGROUND

Overview

A patient's hospital experience has multiple and complex healthcare provider interactions. Ongoing communication is an essential part of ensuring the continuity of care is met and safety is maintained. Accurate communication between providers contributes to increased patient safety (Robinson, 2016). In the operating room (OR), communication is emphasized and clarified through briefings (focused review of activities with all members of the team pre-procedure) and debriefings (focused review of activities with all members of the team post-procedure) designed to improve teamwork and prevent errors. Briefings and debriefings in the OR are processes where interdisciplinary team members have an opportunity to plan and discuss events before and after a surgery or procedure (Carbines, 2017). Failure to perform a debriefing or conducting a debriefing incorrectly can lead to preventable errors. These errors contribute to lapses in patient safety ranging from incorrect documentation resulting in the recording of the wrong procedure or wrong instrument/supply counts post-procedure to mismanaged specimens resulting in inaccurate diagnoses. While incorrect documentation could lead to missed diagnosis and/or missed revenue, more importantly, mismanaged/missed specimens could be life threatening such as in the case of a missed potential cancer biopsy specimen.

The OR is a high-risk and task saturated environment where surgeons, nurses, and staff must practice effective communication skills to ensure safe care. However, lack of effective communication is a common cause of adverse events that occur in the OR (Kleiner, Link, Maynard, & Carpenter, 2014). The Joint Commission (TJC) has identified

ineffective communication as a critical contributor to events related to patient safety regarding healthcare (TJC, 2012). Regulatory agencies have made communication a priority component to be addressed as part of patient safety initiatives (Robinson, 2016). In 2009, the World Health Organization (WHO) implemented the surgical safety checklist (SSC) with the intention of decreasing errors and improving teamwork and communication in the OR and procedural areas (WHO, 2018). The debriefing process is an essential element of the SSC and it contributes to a culture of effective communication that is vital to ensure patient safety (Donnelly, 2017).

There are many circumstances that make the OR an environment at high-risk for potential errors. Situational awareness, effective communication, and organization are just a few of the skills required by all team members in the OR to prevent or minimize errors (Marshall & Finlayson, 2018). Debriefings are an important part of the surgical environment that optimize patient safety by providing an opportunity to: clarify necessary documentation, facilitate accurate specimen management through verbal/written, double check confirmation, identify opportunities for improvement by sharing observations, and collaborate about next steps in the continuum of care. Not only is debriefing a method to optimize learning and improve performance (Ahmed, Sevdalis, Vincent, & Arora, 2013), studies have shown post-procedural debriefings are instrumental in improving overall patient safety (Magill et al., 2017).

The OR in a busy, urban medical center in Southern California where the author had practiced, has had several adverse events that may have been prevented if the required debriefing process had been conducted properly. The leadership team of the surgical service department developed a debrief checklist to guide staff in the OR to use

the correct process for initiation and completion of a debriefing. This checklist was to be used as an audit tool to track the implementation progress of and compliance with the debriefings process. Currently, debriefing is part of the standard practice for post-procedure review. However, observed compliance and incompleteness of the data on those that are performed indicate that personnel do not appear to value its use. Further still, anecdotal reports by staff have referred to the checklist as part of the “tick-box culture” which negates the purpose of the tool and allows errors to occur.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) quality improvement (QI) project is to identify the barriers to proper use of the debriefing process and then to improve the debriefing process as part of the SSC in the OR. This will be achieved through the following specific objectives: a) identify operating room staff perceptions of barriers to an effective debriefing process; b) develop and implement an evidence-based standard procedure that incorporates the debriefing process by targeting and mitigating identified barriers and assess knowledge of the debriefing process pre and post implementation of the new procedure and c) evaluate staff team members intent to change practice and use a new, revised standardized debriefing process.

Supporting Framework

A blended theoretical model and conceptual framework served as the lens for analysis of the problem and how the proposed solution will address the problem. First, the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice served as the conceptual model for implementation of practice change. The IOWA Model of Evidence-Based Practice provides the framework for implementation of the evidence-based practice, debriefing.

Then, the Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change (TTM) served as the model for analyzing the staff members willingness to change their behavior. The TTM explains a human's desire to change behavior within the context of stages that must be learned and then embraced before a true change is made. The synthesis of the two models occurs when the author is able to develop and incorporate the evidence-based practice (EBP) (debriefing process) into a standard practice procedure because the OR staff understand why it is important to patient safety and are willing to change behavior in order to successfully reduce errors and maintain safety post-procedure.

Iowa Model

Updated in 2015 by the Iowa Model Collaborative, the Iowa Model Revised, further referred to as the Iowa Model (Figure 1), is an effective tool to lead EBP-driven changes. When a change includes EBP as a catalyst, the Iowa Model can serve as a template for organizing the process from start to finish (Lloyd, D'Errico, & Bristol, 2016). The Iowa model is often used to guide implementation of EBP and serves as a very specific diagram to achieve the process improvement goal. The Iowa Model consists of a seven-step process for change (Doody & Doody, 2011). The first step is to identify a problem-focused trigger; an opportunity for improvement. The second step is to state the problem. In this DNP project, the identified need for change is to improve the fidelity of the debriefing process in the OR. To improve fidelity of the debriefing is to enhance the commitment to communicating important information at the end of a surgical case with the intent of increasing patient safety, or otherwise referred to as improving the safety through a more reliable and efficient process. The Iowa Model offers three decision point opportunities to direct the project. The first decision point is to decide if

the presented topic is a priority for the organization. This is an urgency for the organization as there have been recent errors or adverse events that may have been prevented if a proper debriefing had been done. This aligns with the organization's stated value of Excellence through teamwork, commitment, accountability, and quality improvement. However, staff may not recognize the urgency of the problem or if a problem exists, therefore not recognizing a need for change. It is at this point that the TTM can assist with identification of the need to improve debriefings as a priority.

The next step is to form a team (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The plan is to organize and facilitate a focus group of multidisciplinary team members and/or stakeholders to create ownership and to collaborate on a process to identify barriers and ultimately improve debriefing in the OR (White & Spruce, 2015). Literature or evidence needs to be reviewed, evaluated, and synthesized in step four of the Iowa model (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). This is also the platform for the second decision point; is the evidence sufficient to support change? Current reviews show a plethora of literature regarding the challenges of the debriefing process. Several studies have been done on different aspects of barriers to debriefing and potential improvements on motivating a team to perform debriefings (Bergs et al., 2015; Magill et al., 2017) thus confirming the evidence is sufficient to guide implementation into practice.

Step five of the Iowa model is to develop a standard of EBP and an implementation plan to execute the change (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The focus of developing a standardized process is to examine best practices that support consistency and value of the debriefing process. Part of the proposed plan will include focus group interviews that target the existing workflow intended for debriefing but has

been observed to not include debriefing. A plan will be developed on how to standardize the debriefing process to ensure the willingness and need to perform the debrief.

The focus of this DNP project is to develop a standard process to improve the quality, consistency, and fidelity of debriefings in the operating room. While the IOWA model provides the framework for implementation of EBP change, it does not address the human desire to change. A model for addressing the desire through actual change in behavior was identified in the literature. It is here that the TTM can assist with influencing the team that a change in practice behavior is indeed needed.

Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change

The TTM explains behavior change through a series of stages; beginning with no recognition of need for a behavior change and ending with the maintenance of change (Prochaska & Prochaska, 2016). The TTM explains why and how certain individuals may be unmotivated, resistant, or unaware of the need for change (Prochaska, 2009). Precontemplation is the first stage where there is no intention of change. The lack of recognition of the need for change may be attributed to a lack of knowledge of the problem (Prochaska, 2008). Therefore, it is necessary to communicate to the group of the identified concerns with the current debriefing process. The second stage, contemplation, shows a willingness to change, but uncertainty on how and when to change. The preparation stage is more promising with plans to change in the near future. Action is the stage where evident changes in behavior have occurred. The phases of change are followed with the next two stages of the TTM, maintenance and relapse or termination. The TTM serves as a decision-making platform to articulate the process of intentional

behavior change for the OR team and is found to be specifically helpful in the early stages of change.

The intent of this DNP project is to develop a standard procedure to improve the consistency and quality of the debriefing process in the OR. The Iowa model can guide the process to implement a standardized procedure while the TTM identifies and recognizes the behavior changes made in progression both in alignment with the goal of improving the debriefing process. The decision to blend two frameworks for this project was investigated by the author and identified as the most efficient way to explain best practice dissemination after addressing core problems related to the identified lack of staff understanding of the relationship between behavior change and safety.

Figure 1. Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care.

Used/reprinted with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics, copyright 2015. For permission to use or reproduce, please contact the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics at 319-384-9098.

STAGES OF CHANGE

Figure 2. Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change (TTM)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Search Methods and Results

A literature search was conducted using the following electronic databases: PubMed CINAHL, EBSCO, Clinical Key, and Google Scholar. The search results yielded 6,952 articles. In addition, a reference list review of selected articles was used to identify additional literature. Search terms included: debriefing, communication, operating room, OR, surgery, hand-off, checklist, errors, safety, patient safety, interprofessional communication, and barriers to debriefing/communication. Publications related to debriefings following surgery or procedure were included. The search was limited to peer reviewed articles published in the English language between 2012-2018. Publications related to debriefing used as a feedback tool to enhance training or education were excluded.

A secondary literature search, using the aforementioned databases was conducted to evaluate research on behavior change, motivating teams, and team dynamics in the operating / procedure room. Key search terms included: human factors, teamwork, team dynamics, communication, trust, team building, non-verbal communication, surgical team, culture of safety, culture, leadership styles, leadership traits, emotional intelligence, and behavior. Inclusion criteria consisted of studies which were concentrated on debriefings, teamwork, and communication in the OR and published in English. Peer-reviewed articles identified in the secondary search that were not published in English were excluded.

Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 28 articles were chosen to augment this proposal and nine were used to construct a table of evidence on identified topics of interest as they occur and relate to the OR setting (see Table 3).

Overview

The aim of this DNP project is to improve the fidelity of the debriefing process which should ultimately reduce errors (adverse events and outcomes) in the OR. The author sought to achieve this goal by improving the culture in the OR through identification and removal of barriers that create inconsistent use and lack of trustworthiness in the debriefing procedure. The literature was searched relating to the following identified topics of interest as they relate to the operating room setting: debriefing in the operating room, teamwork and team dynamics in the operating room, communication, and barriers to communication and debriefing in the operating room.

Debriefing in the OR

Debriefing is the third phase of the SSC and is also the phase that is completed or performed the least (Anderson, Appelbaum, Bartz-Kurycki, Tsao, & Browne, 2018; Bartz-Kurycki et al., 2017; Magill et al., 2017; Singer et al., 2016; Zukerman, France, Green, Leming-Lee, Anders, & Mocco, 2012). Debriefings allow for discussion about failures or near failures as well as successes. Additionally, debriefings have been suggested to improve communication and teamwork, decrease adverse events and/or errors, and enhance efficiency (Bartz-Kurycki et al., 2017; Garrett, 2016; Magill et al., 2017; Singer et al., 2016; Zukerman et al., 2012). Further, debriefings can also promote awareness and above all, improve patient safety (Singer et al., 2016; Zukerman et al., 2012). Standardizing the debriefing is one way to enhance the transfer of critical

information required for continuity of care as well as providing consistency in how the debriefing is performed (Kleiner et al., 2014; Robinson, 2016; Savage et al., 2017; Singer et al., 2016).

Teamwork and Team Dynamics

Successful healthcare outcomes today are due in large part to a well-functioning team process. The critical need for a successfully functioning team effort could not be more evident than in the operating room (Dahl et al., 2017; Wakeman & Langham, 2018; Weller, Boyd, & Cumin, 2014). It is well documented that in interprofessional environments, highly functioning teams promote efficiency in care, improved outcomes, and most importantly, a culture of safety (Dahl et al., 2017; Marshall & Finlayson, 2018; Sonoda, Onozuka, & Hagihara, 2017; Wakeman & Langham, 2018; Weller et al., 2014). In fact, the Institute of Medicine report *To Err is Human* proclaimed effective team functioning as a key component of the safe hospitals' initiative (Wakeman & Langham, 2018; Donaldson, Corrigan, & Kohn, 2000). Teamwork is identified as a non-technical skill (NTS) along with communication, situational awareness, and shared decision making (Marshall & Finlayson, 2018; Savage et al., 2017; Siu, Maran, & Paterson-Brown, 2014). It is reported that failure in execution of these NTSs can be attributed to preventable adverse events in the operating room (Anderson et al., 2018; Wahr et al., 2013; Wakeman & Langham, 2018; Weller et al., 2014). Training staff to effectively engage in these types of NTS can help to reduce these adverse events. In addition, discussions of high-functioning teams describe a democratic environment of flattened hierarchy, where every team member is valued and has a voice thereby encouraging open

communication (Singer et al., 2016; Skinner, Holdefer, McAuliffe, & Sala, 2017; Wahr et al., 2013; Wakeman & Langham, 2018; Weller et al., 2014).

Communication

Communication plays an important role in successful teamwork processes. Many adverse events that occur in healthcare are attributed to communication failures (Garrett, 2016; Robinson, 2016; Siu, Maran, Paterson-Brown, 2014; Wahr et al., 2013; Wakeman & Langham, 2018). Of the several NTSs identified for healthcare providers, communication is the most influential in practice (Marshall & Finlayson, 2018). A culture of safety is heightened with effective communication; specifically, communication that is standardized, concise, appropriate, and well planned (Garrett, 2016; Putnam et al., 2014; Robinson, 2016; Savage et al., 2017). Standardizing communication improves teamwork and can facilitate the transfer of essential and exceptional information which can ultimately lead to a reduction in errors and an increase in patient safety (Anderson, Appelbaum et al., 2018; Bartz-Kurycki et al., 2017; Garrett, 2016; Magill et al., 2017; Skinner et al., 2017; Wahr et al., 2013).

Barriers to Communication and Debriefing

Debriefings are intended to enhance communication between surgical team members to improve team performance and to improve outcomes (Hicks, Rosen, Hobson, Ko, & Wick, 2014). However, several factors can make this communication challenging. One of the most compelling barriers to effective communication is staff and physician perception to the existing safety culture. Literature reports that if the culture of safety is poor, compliance to debriefing and or other safety measures will be poor as well (Bergs et al., 2015; Hicks et al., 2014; Kleiner et al., 2014; Levy et al., 2012; Magill et al., 2017;

Putnam et al., 2014; Wahr et al., 2013). Several studies recommend a staff assessment of safety culture in the form of a survey or questionnaire to help identify challenges (Carbines, 2017; Dahl, et al., 2017; Kleiner et al., 2014; Levy et al., 2012; Magill et al., 2017; Savage et al., 2017; Weller et al., 2014; Zuckerman et al., 2012). Also, of importance for debriefing implementation is physician buy-in to the process (Carbines, 2017; Hicks et al., 2014; Kleiner et al., 2014; Singer et al., 2016; Zuckerman et al., 2012). Other barriers mentioned include: incorporation into an electronic health record (EHR) (Weller et al., 2014; Zuckerman et al., 2012); timing of debrief (Anderson et al., 2018; Levy et al., 2012); cumbersome and inappropriate checklist items (Anderson et al., 2018); and lastly, stakeholder ownership (Anderson et al., 2018; Bergs et al., 2015; Carbines, 2017; Hicks et al., 2014; Zuckerman et al., 2012).

Proposed Solutions

Creating a patient experience in the OR free from preventable errors is an achievable goal. It is theorized that employing tools such as checklists including debriefing, prevents errors and make it possible to achieve this goal. Barriers to performing debriefings include, but are not limited to: physician acceptance, absent or delayed communication, teamwork challenges, and stakeholder involvement to name a few (Bartz-Kurycki et al., 2017; Bergs et al., 2015; Kleiner et al., 2014; Levy et al., 2012). Standardization is mentioned in several studies along with stakeholder inclusion for design to ensure successful implementation, fidelity, and sustainment of any proposed interventions (Bartz-Kurycki et al., 2017; Wakeman & Langham, 2018). The proposed plan to solve this problem is to form a team of engaged stakeholders to identify barriers to consistent use of the debriefing process. The proposed solution is then to develop and

implement a standardized procedure that enhances commitment to use of debriefing through the mitigation of these stakeholder identified barriers and create awareness of the relationship between healthcare personnel perception and behavior of the debriefing process and its direct link to patient safety.

Summary of Literature

Debriefings in the operating room have been shown to be an effective communication tool to prevent adverse events and errors (Zuckerman et al., 2012). Studies have also demonstrated low fidelity after the novelty of the debriefing procedure as an intervention to increase efficiency has worn off (Putnam et al., 2014). Several barriers have been identified and there are minimal studies on how to maintain meaningful use of debriefing checklists as a consistent communication process in the OR. The leadership of the OR at the medical center gave permission and support for this project due to recently occurring near miss and actual events that may have been prevented had a proper debriefing process been performed. It has been suggested that one way to successfully change the behavior toward the quality of consistency and staff compliance with OR debriefing is through development of a standardized procedure that specifically addresses staff-identified barriers (Putnam et al., 2014). It is with this strategy that this DNP project will attempt to decrease errors in the OR through improving the fidelity of the debriefing process.

METHODS

Design

The study design intended to be used in this QI project was a nonexperimental pre and post-test design. The goal was to use three (3) instruments- the Modified Safety Attitudes Questionnaire (SAQ), the Confidence Scale (C-Scale), and the Organizational Readiness for Intent to Change (ORIC) to examine staff perceptions of safety, confidence in debriefing pre/post new standard work implementation, and intent to change practice and use the new standard work process, respectively. However, as the project was initiated, the author left the organization due to unforeseen circumstances beyond the author's control. Due to access, timing constraints, and unexpected organizational administrative changes, the project was modified within the original approved Institutional Review Board (IRB) project guidelines, at the request of the organization's new leadership to accommodate these challenges and still produce a meaningful QI project for the medical center. The following represents the final study design. First, the author conducted a baseline evaluation of all interested OR staff members (including registered nurses (RNs), registered nurse first-assistants (RNFAs), surgical technologists (STs), anesthesia technologists (ATs), and core technologists) perceptions of the culture of safety in the OR using the modified SAQ survey as originally designed. Although original IRB approval included physicians, time and access limitations precluded physician participation. The intent of the baseline evaluation survey was to reveal if staff perceived safety as a priority in their clinical practice and if they believed they were performing debriefings as part of that culture of safety. Next, interested staff participated in a validated survey to self-assess their confidence in performance of the current

debriefing procedure using the C-Scale survey as the project was originally designed. Then, due to the aforementioned organizational changes, this concluded the QI project as it was originally designed, and the assessment/data collection stage of the project was concluded, and data was presented to the medical center OR leadership team. Instead of completing the development of a new standard work procedure for debriefing and assessing its implementation, the project was modified to only provide these actions as recommendations to the new leadership in the OR at the medical center. The author met with the new leadership in the OR to present the results from the safety and confidence surveys and suggest recommendations. The author then met with OR staff during a scheduled, daily, morning huddle to share the results of the surveys and discuss the evidence that supports the need for improving debriefings. Finally, the author shared the recommendation of standardizing the elements and timing of debriefing in a manner that will facilitate use of a debriefing process that the author believes will improve the fidelity of debriefings and contribution toward safety. The future goal, post DNP project, will be for the OR leadership team at the medical center to use this information to increase patient safety by showing staff they can reduce adverse events occurring in the OR through the implementation and use of this new standardized procedure that links the debriefing process and staff behavior to patient safety.

Ethical Considerations

A letter of approval for commencement of this project was requested and received from the Chief Nursing Officer at the medical center. Data collected from the safety assessment survey was deidentified as necessary and evaluated by the author. All

surveys and the questionnaire were performed with Survey Monkey via the Learning Management System (LMS) at the medical center.

Prior to implementation, IRB applications were submitted to both the medical center and California State University, Los Angeles requesting exemption status and approval was granted.

Sample and Setting

The project was implemented at a twelve-suite surgical department in a 320-bed, acute care medical center. All surgical staff ~~were~~ currently working in the surgery department were asked to participate. Although the original plan was to include physician providers, due to the aforementioned time and organizational change restraints, surgeons and anesthesiologists were excluded.

Instruments

There were three instruments approved for use in collecting data for this DNP QI project: 1) The Modified Safety Attitudes Questionnaire (SAQ) used to assess the perceived culture of safety, 2) The intended use for Confidence Scale (C-Scale) survey was to assess pre and post standardized procedure implementation staff perceptions of knowledge, and confidence in performing the debriefing process, and 3) the intended use for Modified Organizational Readiness for Intent to Change (ORIC) survey was to assess post implementation readiness to change. The final use for the C-Scale was in a pre-test manner only as the post-test was not able to be conducted due to time limitations. Similarly, the ORIC survey was not administered since the revision to the standardized debriefing process was not completed due to access and time limitations. Lastly,

demographic practice data concerning role and years in the practice setting were collected.

Safety Attitudes Questionnaire

Results of the SAQ were analyzed to assess staff perception of the organizational culture of safety. The questionnaire uses a Likert-type scale to measure attitudes and beliefs about the aspects of safe practice that are important to the surgical team. The SAQ is considered a reliable tool and permission was obtained for use (Sexton et al., 2006). (See Appendix E). The SAQ was modified by using a reduced number of questions from the instrument as a consideration of staff 's time participation availability (See Appendix A).

The Confidence Scale

The original plan included pre and post results from the C-Scale to show if knowledge and confidence were gained after the implementation of the standardized debriefing process. This survey uses a Likert-type scale to assess the self-efficacy of staff in performing debriefings. (See Appendix B). The C-Scale is a validated and reliable tool and permission was obtained for use. (Grundy, 1993). (See Appendix F). Again, due to access and time limitations, only the pre-C-Scale survey assessment was completed.

Organizational Readiness for Intent to Change

The ORIC was intended to be performed post education regarding the standardized process for debriefing to assess staff's psychological and behavioral readiness in regard to change. The survey uses a Likert-type scale and is considered valid and reliable (Shea et al., 2014). The ORIC was modified to reduce the number of

questions in consideration of staff's time participation availability (See Appendix C). Permission was obtained for use (See Appendix G) however, due to access and time limitations this survey assessment was not performed.

Data Collection and Intervention

The review of literature demonstrated several key factors for encouraging compliance with the debriefing process; standardization being the most common element (Singer et al., 2016). The following steps were initiated for the implementation and evaluation of this QI project. First, the SAQ (Sexton et al., 2006) was slightly modified (only selected questions that assessed perceptions of safety were used) and then assigned to all staff in the OR via the medical center's LMS. Second, a single evaluation of the staff's current confidence in performing a debriefing using the C-Scale survey was also administered via the hospital LMS. Additionally, demographic practice data was collected as part of the SAQ. Participation was voluntary and encouraged with verbal reminders from leadership in the OR, and electronic reminders via email. Results of the surveys were protected via an online survey tool to capture the perceptions of the staff. The results were analyzed via Excel and SPSS version 23 and assessed to guide the intervention steps. The revised intervention was a presentation of the results to the new OR leadership team which helped provide them with information that demonstrated "why" the current debriefing process needed to be improved.

RESULTS

Findings

The results of this QI project relate to the initial C-Scale assessment, the modified SAQ, and the practice demographic data. The SAQ results revealed, 42 out of 81 OR staff assigned responded for a response rate of 51.9%. See Table 1 for SAQ and Demographic Role/Practice Counts and Frequencies Data.

Table 1

Modified SAQ and Demographics of the Medical Center OR Staff

Variables	<i>M (SD)</i>	Frequency (Valid %)
SAQ	4.05 (1.125)	
<i>Q#4-Debriefings are common in the OR.</i>		
5 = Strongly agree		19 (45.2%)
4 = Agree slightly		13 (31.0%)
3 = Neutral		4 (9.5%)
2 = Disagree slightly		5 (11.9%)
1 = Strongly disagree		1 (2.4%)
<i>Position/Role</i>		
RN	4.26 (0.701)	24 (57.1%)
Surgical Technologist	4.14 (0.613)	9 (21.4%)
Anesthesia Technicians	3.98 (1.097)	2 (4.8%)
Core Technicians	4.29 (0.453)	1 (2.4%)
Registered Nurse, First Assistant	4.05 (0.748)	6 (14.3%)
<i>Years Practice in OR: OR Experience</i>		
<1	4.16 (0.675)	2 (4.8%)
1-2		5 (11.9%)
3-4		2 (4.8%)
5-10		5 (11.9%)
11-20		15 (35.7%)
21<		13 (31.0%)

Missing data = 0

For the C-Scale, 44 of 81 responded in one out of five questions for a response rate of 54.3%. Forty-three (43) out of 81 responded in two out of five questions and 42 in two out of five for response rates of 53.1% and 51.9%, respectively. Overall, this represented a significant participation rate which can be considered as a reasonable and representative sample of the OR staff. Demographic practice and role related data revealed an experienced OR staff with 61.7% having 11 or more years of experience. See Table 2 for C-Scale and Practice Counts and Frequencies Data.

Key results from the modified SAQ revealed only 45.24% of the staff “strongly agreed” that debriefings were a common practice currently in the OR while the remaining 55.76% responses ranged from ‘slightly agree’ to ‘strongly disagree’. Additionally, responses to all five of the C-Scale questions ranged from 44.19 to 63.64% in which they felt they were not absolutely certain they were performing the debriefing process correctly, without hesitation, competently, assuredly, or satisfactorily. These results identified staff’s lack of awareness of the link between poor (less than absolute confidence) in their performance related to the debriefing process and the perceived relationship of the debriefing process to a culture of safety.

Table 2

C-Scale Practice Counts and Frequencies

Variables	<i>M (SD)</i> Min-Max [Range]	Frequency (Valid %)
C-Scale Q #1-I am certain that my debriefing performance is correct	4.25 (.686) 2-5 [3]	
5 = Absolutely certain for all steps		16 (36.4%)
4 = Certain for almost all steps		24 (54.5%)
3 = Fairly certain for a good number of steps		3 (6.8%)
2 = Certain for only a few steps		1 (2.3%)
1 = not at all certain		0 (0.0%)
C-Scale Q#2 – I feel that I perform debriefing without hesitation	4.28 (.701) 0-5 [5]	
5 = Absolutely no hesitation		24 (54.5%)
4 = Almost completely without hesitation		16 (36.4%)
3 = A good part of it without hesitation		2 (4.5%)
2 = A fair amount of hesitation		0 (0.0%)
1 = I have much hesitation		1 (2.3%)
C-Scale Q#3 – My performance would convince an observer that I'm competent at debriefing	4.47 (.702) 0-5 [5]	
5 = For absolutely all of it		24 (54.5%)
4 = for almost of all of it		16 (36.4%)
3 = For much of it		2 (4.5%)
2 = Agree a little		1 (2.3%)
1 = Not at all		1 (2.3%)
C-Scale Q#4 – I feel sure of myself as I perform debriefing	4.42 (.545) 0-5 [5]	
5 = For Absolutely all of it		19 (43.2%)
4 = For almost all of it		23 (52.3%)
3 = For much of it		1 (2.3%)
2 = Very Little		0 (0.0%)
1 = Not at all		1 (2.3%)
C-Scale Q#5 – I feel satisfied with my debriefing performance	4.31 (.749) 0-5 [5]	
5 = Absolutely satisfied with all of it		19 (43.2%)
4 = For almost all of it		18 (40.9%)
3 = For much of it		4 (9.1%)
2 = Very little		1 (2.3%)
1 = Not at all		2 (4.5%)

Missing data = 0

Evaluation

This project was implemented and evaluated using a survey methodology. First, the modified SAQ survey was administered to participants to assess their perceived culture of safety as it relates to debriefing as an evidence-based best practice for ensuring a safe environment. The C-Scale survey was used to assess staff knowledge and confidence in performing debriefings as they are intended to be performed according to the medical center's current standard process for the debriefing procedure. Demographic practice data was collected to provide additional background as to the roles and experience levels of staff in the OR. In the original project plan, the ORIC survey was to be used to assess the staff members willingness to change their practice, post implementation of the new standardized procedure for debriefing. However, due to time constraints for this project, this survey assessment was not performed. The evaluation of the project occurred through review and analysis of the survey data with presentation of the results to the OR leadership team and staff at the medical center.

DISCUSSION

Although this project had an unexpected change in its course, significant information was revealed from the performance and completion of this project. First, a big revelation was the connection between the culture of safety and task performance in the operating room. While the SAQ was used to assess the staff's perceived culture of safety, the unexpected results created the need for an alternate focus on linking the culture to practices such as debriefing as a priority, prior to implementation of a new standardized procedure for debriefing. The new focus needed to encompass the staff's lack of recognition of the poor culture of safety. This was evidenced by data collected in which staff felt the organization was performing safely and conducting debriefings when in all reality, the practice was not consistent. Moreover, the author identified a problem with the underreporting of adverse events and/or errors also contributing to the lack of recognition of the adverse culture. Nonetheless, leadership was conflicted with regards to reporting of issues with performance or failures in performance, as data was nonexistent.

In their book on safety strategies, Vincent & Amalberti discussed the theory that safety must be a constantly evolving and modified concept (2016). Short-term fixes or workarounds become common practice for front-line staff to cope with the demands of ever-growing responsibilities; maximizing task completion without real consideration of safety. In an article on accident analysis and prevention, the authors described the term culture or "a system of beliefs, meanings, norms, and values" as likely behaviors defining "the way we have always done it" and how this level of misidentification does not lead to problem solving or improvement (Myers, Nyce, & Dekker, 2014, p.29). The authors suggest examining behaviors and structures to identify the problem instead of the culture

as a whole and in its place, look at individual contributors to the problem (Myers et al., 2014). One suggested focus is the breakdown in teamwork where staff do not feel comfortable speaking up or are perhaps bullied when trying to do the right thing.

Part of managing safety is to try to eliminate errors; a bigger part is recognizing the inevitability of the task. It is undisputed that teams produce better outcomes in dynamic clinical environments, such as operating rooms. A team can create a safety net when we acknowledge that errors are inevitable and collaborating as a team can make errors avoidable (Vincent & Amalberti, 2016). This means executing tasks such as the safety checklists as the opportunity they are; to reflect and to perform at best, free from errors.

Some limitations of this project were limited access, timing constraints, the author's change in status, and leadership changes. These contributed to a change in focus regarding the priorities of the project however, the data collected revealed the depth of the issue concerning the lack of staff's understanding of the link between a culture of safety and the fidelity of the debriefing process. Additionally, another limitation was the methodology used to assess the study question. Conceivably, a mixed method assessment of the culture of safety would produce a more robust set of data as suggested in a literature review on assessing culture of safety in the hospital setting (Pumar-Mendez, Attree, & Wakefield, 2014). For instance, a qualitative study represented by a questionnaire does not necessarily provide an in-depth view of an individual's assessment of perceived culture. Staff may become unconsciously influenced by the culture they are imbedded in making identification of detrimental behaviors unrecognizable (Pumar-Mendez et al., 2014). This is why a mixed method, such as personal interviews, focus

groups, and observations along with quantitative data collection from reported adverse events would have contributed added enhancement to data and findings when attempting to evaluate an organizations culture of safety. Conceivably, staff engagement could be a predictor of the true culture of safety as well (Vincent & Amalberti, 2016). Therefore, to gain a more realistic picture of the culture of a group or team, it is suggested a more in-depth approach be taken in the assessment of a problem so that a customized approach to improvement can be developed. Lastly, the lack of physician participation was viewed as another limitation which the author felt would have been a valuable contribution to the SAQ and C-Scale surveys.

SUMMARY

This was a tremendous learning opportunity for the author in that identifying the problem required much more investigation than had originally been afforded to this project. The author was disappointed that the original goal was not able to be completed as designed. However, the modification to the process produced results that were not anticipated yet were found to be as, if not more, useful in addressing the original questions posed in the project. Failure can be defined as “lack of success” as in the case of this project “falling short” of the intended goal (Failure, 2019). It can be argued that failure can be a part of success and an occasion to learn and develop (Simpson & Maltese, 2017). The author changed strategies and instead reflected on what could be produced from the accomplishments that led up to the point of recognition in which the project needed a different direction; namely, the suggestion that perhaps staff needed education and assistance with event reporting, recognizing the opportunities for improvement in the organizational culture of safety, and with confidence in performing debriefings.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, M., Sevdalis, N., Vincent, C., & Arora, S. (2013). Actual vs. Perceived performance debriefing in surgery: Practice far from perfect. *The American Journal of Surgery*, 205(4), 434-440. doi: 10.1016/j.amjsurg.2013.01.007
- Anderson, K. T., Appelbaum, R., Bartz-Kurycki, M. A., Tsao, K., & Browne, M. (2018). Advances in perioperative quality and safety. *Seminars in Pediatric Surgery* 27, (2), 92-101. Elsevier. doi: 10.1053/j.sempedsurg.2018.02.006
- Bartz-Kurycki, M. A., Anderson, K. T., Abraham, J. E., Masada, K. M., Wang, J., Kawaguchi, A. L., . . . & Tsao, K. (2017). Debriefing: the forgotten phase of the surgical safety checklist. *Journal of Surgical Research*, 213, 222-227. doi: 10.1016/j.iss.2017.02.072
- Bergs, J., Lambrechts, F., Simons, P., Vlayen, A., Marneffe, W., Hellings, J., . . . & Vandijck, D. (2015). Barriers and facilitators related to the implementation of surgical safety checklists: A systematic review of the qualitative evidence. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, bmjqs-2015. doi: 10.1136/bmjqs-2015-004021
- Brown, C. G. (2014). The Iowa model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care: An illustrated example in oncology nursing. *Clinical journal of oncology nursing*, 18(2), 157-159. doi: 10.1188/14.CJON.157-159
- Carbines, M. (2017). Briefing and debriefing in two Auckland ORL suites. *Dissector*, 44(4), 16-19.

- Dahl, A. B., Abdallah, A. B., Maniar, H., Avidan, M. S., Bollini, M. L., Patterson, G. A., . . . & Ridley, C. H. (2017). Building a collaborative culture in cardiothoracic operating rooms: Pre and post-intervention study protocol for evaluation of the implementation of TeamSTEPPS training and the impact on perceived psychological safety. *BMJ Open*, 7(9), e017389. doi: 10.1136/bjmopen-2017-017389
- Donaldson, M. S., Corrigan, J. M., & Kohn, L. T. (Eds.). (2000). To err is human: Building a safer health system. *Institute of Medicine*, 6. National Academies Press.
- Donnelly, T. (2017). Leadership: Briefing and debriefing in the operating room. *Journal of Perioperative Practice*, 27(7), 154-157. doi: 10.1177/1750458917027007-802
- Doody, C. M., & Doody, O. (2011). Introducing evidence into nursing practice: Using the IOWA model. *British Journal of Nursing*, 20(11), 661-664. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2011.20.11.661
- Failure. 2019. In *Merriam-Webster.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/failure>
- Garrett, J. H. (2016). Effective perioperative communication to enhance patient care. *AORN Journal*, 104(2), 111-120. doi: 10.1016/j.aorn.2016.06.001
- Grundy, S. E. (1993). The confidence scale: development and psychometric characteristics. *Nurse Educator*, 18(1), 6-9. Pollak Library Microfilm RT71 .N74

Hicks, C. W., Rosen, M., Hobson, D. B., Ko, C., & Wick, E. C. (2014). Improving safety and quality of care with enhanced teamwork through operating room briefings. *Journal of the American Medical Association, Surgery*, *149*(8), 863-868. doi: 10.1001/jamasurg.2014.172

Iowa Model Collaborative, Buckwalter, K. C., Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Kleiber, C., McCarthy, A. M., . . . & Authored on behalf of the Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, *14*(3), 175-182. 10.1111/wvn.12223

~~Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, *14*(3), 175-182. doi: 10.1111/wvn.12223~~

Kleiner, C., Link, T., Maynard, M. T., & Carpenter, K. H. (2014). Coaching to improve the quality of communication during briefings and debriefings. *AORN Journal*, *100*(4), 358-368. doi: 10.1016/j.aorn.2014.03.012

Levy, S. M., Senter, C. E., Hawkins, R. B., Zhao, J. Y., Doody, K., Kao, L. S., . . . & Tsao, K. (2012). Implementing a surgical checklist: More than checking a box. *Surgery*, *152*(3), 331-336. doi: 10.1016/j.surg.2012.05.034

Lloyd, S., D'Errico, E., & Bristol, S. (2016). Use of the Iowa model of research in practice as a curriculum framework for Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project completion. *Nurse education perspectives*, *37*(1), 51-53. Doi: 10.5480/14-1364

- Magill, S. T., Wand, D. D., Rutledge, W. C., Lau, D., Berger, M. S., Sankaran, S., Lau, C. Y., Imershein, S. G. (2017). Changing operating room culture: Implementation of a postoperative debrief and improved safety culture. *World Neurosurgery*, *107*, 597-603. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2017.08.090>
- Marshall, D., & Finlayson, M. (2018). Identifying the non-technical skills required of nurses in general surgical wards. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 10.1111/jocn.14290
- Myers, D. J., Nyce, J. M., & Dekker, S. W. (2014). Setting culture apart: Distinguishing culture from behavior and social structure in safety and injury research. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, *68*, 25-29. 10.1016/j.aap.2013.12.010
- Prochaska, J. O. (2008). Decision making in the transtheoretical model of behavior change. *Medical decision making*, *28*(6), 845-849. doi: 10.1177/0272989X08327068
- Prochaska, J. O., & Prochaska, J. M. (2016). Behavior change. In D. B. Nash, R. J. Fabius, A. Skoufalous, & J. L. Clarke (Eds.), *Population health: Creating a culture of wellness* (2nd ed., pp. 115-130). Burlington, MA: Jones & Bartlett Learning.
- Pumar-Méndez, M. J., Attree, M., & Wakefield, A. (2014). Methodological aspects in the assessment of safety culture in the hospital setting: a review of the literature. *Nurse Education Today*, *34*(2), 162-170. 10.1016/j.nedt.2013.08.008
- Putnam, L. R., Levy, S. M., Sajid, M., Dubuisson, D. A., Rogers, N. B., Kao, L. S., . . . & Tsao, K. (2014). Multifaceted interventions improve adherence to the surgical checklist. *Surgery*, *156*(2), 336-344. 10.1016/j.surg.2014.03.032

- Robinson, N. L. (2016). Promoting patient safety with perioperative hand-off communication. *Journal of Perianesthesia Nurses*, 31(3), 245-253. doi: 10.1016/j.jopan.2014.08.144
- Savage, C., Gaffney, F. A., Hussain-Alkhateeb, L., Olsson Ackheim, P., Henricson, G., Antoniadou, I., . . . & Pukk Härenstam, K. (2017). Safer paediatric surgical teams: A 5-year evaluation of crew resource management implementation and outcomes. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 29(6), 853-860. doi: 10.1093/intqhc/mzx113
- Sexton, J. B., Helmreich, R. L., Neilands, T. B., Rowan, K., Vella, K., Boyden, J., . . . & Thomas, E. J. (2006). The Safety Attitudes Questionnaire: psychometric properties, benchmarking data, and emerging research. *BMC health services research*, 6(1), 44. doi: 10.1186/1472-6963-6-44
- Shea, C. M., Jacobs, S. R., Esserman, D. A., Bruce, K., & Weiner, B. J. (2014). Organizational readiness for implementing change: a psychometric assessment of a new measure. *Implementation Science*, 9(1), 7. doi: 10.1186/1748-5908-9-7
- Singer, S. J., Molina, G., Li, Z., Jiang, W., Nurudeen, S., Kite, J. G., . . . & Berry, W. R. (2016). Relationship between operating room teamwork, contextual factors, and safety checklist performance. *Journal of the American College of Surgeons*, 223(4), 568-580. doi: 10.1016/j.jamcollsurg.2016.07.006
- Siu, J., Maran, N., & Paterson-Brown, S. (2016). Observation of behavioural markers of non-technical skills in the operating room and their relationship to intra-operative incidents. *The Surgeon*, 14(3), 119-128. doi: 10.1016/j.surge.2014.06.005

- Skinner, S., Holdefer, R., McAuliffe, J. J., & Sala, F. (2017). Medical error avoidance in intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring: The communication imperative. *Journal of Clinical Neurophysiology*, *34*(6), 477-483. doi: 10.1097/WNP.0000000000000419
- Sonoda, Y., Onozuka, D., & Hagihara, A. (2018). Factors related to teamwork performance and stress of operating room nurses. *Journal of Nursing Management*, *26*(1), 66-73. doi: 10.1111/jonm.12522
- The Joint Commission (2012). Joint Commission center for transforming healthcare releases targeted solutions tool for hand-off communications. *Joint Commission Perspectives*. *32*(8).
- Vincent, C., & Amalberti, R. (2016). Safety strategies in hospitals. In *Safer Healthcare* (pp. 73-91). Springer, Cham.
- Wahr, J. A., Prager, R. L., Abernathy, J. 3., Martinez, E. A., Salas, E., Seifert, P. C., . . . & Sanchez, J. A. (2013). Patient safety in the cardiac operating room: Human factors and teamwork: A scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation*, CIR-0b013e3182a38efa. doi: 10.1161/CIR.0b013e3182a38efa
- Wakeman, D., & Langham, M. R. (2018, April). Creating a safer operating room: Groups, team dynamics and crew resource management principles. In *Seminars in Pediatric Surgery* (Vol. 27, No. 2, pp. 107-113). Elsevier. doi: 10.1053/j.sempedsurg.2018.02.008

- Weller, J., Boyd, M., & Cumin, D. (2014). Teams, tribes and patient safety: Overcoming barriers to effective teamwork in healthcare. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*, postgradmedj-2012. doi: 10.1136/postgradmedj-2012-131168
- White, S., & Spruce, L. (2015). Perioperative nursing leaders implement clinical practice guidelines using the Iowa model of evidence-based practice. *AORN journal*, 102(1), 50-59. doi: 10.1016/j.aorn.2015.04.001
- World Health Organization. (2018). WHO surgical safety checklist. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/patientsafety/topics/safe-surgery/checklist/en/>
- Zuckerman, S. L., France, D. J., Green, C., Leming-Lee, S., Anders, S., & Mocco, J. (2012). Surgical debriefing: A reliable roadmap to completing the patient safety cycle. *Neurosurgical Focus*, 33(5), E4. doi : 10.3171/2012.8.FOCUS12248

APPENDIX A

MODIFIED SAFETY ATTITUDES QUESTIONNAIRE (SAQ)

Choose your response using the scale below:

1	2	3	4	5
Disagree Strongly	Disagree Slightly	Neutral	Agree Slightly	Agree Strongly

1. I would feel safe being treated here as a patient.

1	2	3	4	5

2. Patient safety is constantly reinforced as the priority in the ORs here.

1	2	3	4	5

3. Debriefing OR personnel after a surgical procedure is important for patient safety.

1	2	3	4	5

4. Debriefings are common in the OR.

1	2	3	4	5

5. All the personnel in the ORs here take responsibility for patient safety.

1	2	3	4	5

Use the scale to describe the quality of communication & collaboration you have experience with:

1. Surgeons

Very Low	Low	Adequate	High	Very High
1	2	3	4	5

2. Anesthesiologists

Very Low	Low	Adequate	High	Very High
1	2	3	4	5

3. Surgical Technicians

Very Low	Low	Adequate	High	Very High
1	2	3	4	5

4. Anesthesia Technicians

Very Low	Low	Adequate	High	Very High
1	2	3	4	5

5. RNs

Very Low	Low	Adequate	High	Very High
1	2	3	4	5

6. RNFAs

Very Low	Low	Adequate	High	Very High
1	2	3	4	5

7. Core Technicians

Very Low	Low	Adequate	High	Very High
1	2	3	4	5

Demographic Role and Practice Information

Please choose only one.

1. Position:
 - a. Registered Nurse
 - b. Registered Nurse, First Assistant
 - c. Surgical Technologist
 - d. Anesthesia Technologist
 - e. Core Technologist
 - f. Surgeon
 - g. Anesthesiologist

2. Years in specialty:
 - a. Less than 6 months
 - b. 6-11 months
 - c. 1-2 years
 - d. 3-4 years
 - e. 5-10 years
 - f. 11-20 years
 - g. 21 or more years

APPENDIX B

CONFIDENCE SCALE (C-SCALE)

Directions: Choose the number which best describes how you perceive your current ability to perform a debriefing in the operating room. (Note: Make sure to choose just ONE number.)

Not at all Certain	Certain for only a few steps	Fairly certain for a good number of steps	Certain for almost all steps	Absolutely certain for all steps
1	2	3	4	5

1. I am certain that my debriefing performance is correct:

Not at all Certain	Certain for only a few steps	Fairly certain for a good number of steps	Certain for almost all steps	Absolutely certain for all steps
1	2	3	4	5

2. I feel that I perform debriefing without hesitation:

Not at all Certain	Certain for only a few steps	Fairly certain for a good number of steps	Certain for almost all steps	Absolutely certain for all steps
1	2	3	4	5

3. My performance would convince an observer that I'm competent at debriefing:

Not at all Certain	Certain for only a few steps	Fairly certain for a good number of steps	Certain for almost all steps	Absolutely certain for all steps
1	2	3	4	5

4. I feel sure of myself as I perform debriefing:

Not at all Certain	Certain for only a few steps	Fairly certain for a good number of steps	Certain for almost all steps	Absolutely certain for all steps
1	2	3	4	5

5. I feel satisfied with my debriefing performance:

Not at all Certain	Certain for only a few steps	Fairly certain for a good number of steps	Certain for almost all steps	Absolutely certain for all steps
1	2	3	4	5

APPENDIX C

**MODIFIED ORGANIZATIONAL READINESS FOR IMPLEMENTING
CHANGE (ORIC) SURVEY**

Please choose your response using the scale below:

Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neutral	Slightly Agree	Agree
1	2	3	4	5

1. We are committed to implementing this change.

1	2	3	4	5

2. We are motivated to implement this change.

1	2	3	4	5

3. We want to implement this change.

1	2	3	4	5

4. We need to implement this change.

1	2	3	4	5

5. We believe this change will work.

1	2	3	4	5

6. We feel that implementing this change is a good idea.

1	2	3	4	5

7. We value this change.

1	2	3	4	5

APPENDIX D**IOWA MODEL PERMISSION TO USE**

From: Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics [mailto:noreply@qualtrics-survey.com]
Sent: Sunday, February 25, 2018 3:58 PM
To: Thompson, Rita
Subject: Permission to Use The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

You have permission, as requested today, to review and/or reproduce *The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care*. Click the link below to open.

[The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care](#)

Copyright is retained by University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics. **Permission is not granted for placing on the internet.**

Citation: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing, 14(3), 175-182*. doi: 10.1111/wvn.12223

In written material, please add the following statement:

Used/reprinted with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics, copyright 2015. For permission to use or reproduce, please contact the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics at 319-384-9098.

Please contact UIHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

APPENDIX E

SAFETY ATTITUDES QUESTIONNAIRE PERMISSION TO USE

Medical School

University of Texas at Houston-Memorial Hermann
Center for Healthcare Quality and Safety

May 9, 2018

Dear Rita Thompson,

You have our permission to use any of the following Safety Attitudes Questionnaires and the corresponding scoring keys:

- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire – Short Form
- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire – Teamwork and Safety Climate
- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire – Ambulatory Version
- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire – ICU Version
- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire – Labor and Delivery Version
- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire – Operating Room Version
- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire – Pharmacy Version
- Safety Climate Survey

Please note, we do not have editable versions for any of the SAQ surveys but feel free to modify the surveys to meet your research endeavors.

Respectfully,

University of Texas at Houston-Memorial Hermann
Center for Healthcare Quality and Safety Team

APPENDIX F

THE CONFIDENCE SCALE PERMISSION TO USE

WOLTERS KLUWER HEALTH, INC. LICENSE TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Feb 02, 2019

This Agreement between Rita Thompson ("You") and Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc. ("Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc.") consists of your license details and the terms and conditions provided by Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc. and Copyright Clearance Center.

License Number	4521060533471
License date	Feb 02, 2019
Licensed Content Publisher	Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc.
Licensed Content Publication	Nurse Educator
Licensed Content Title	The Confidence Scale: Development and Psychometric Characteristics
Licensed Content Author	Susan Grundy
Licensed Content Date	Sep 1, 1992
Licensed Content Volume	17
Licensed Content Issue	5
Type of Use	Dissertation/Thesis
Requestor type	Individual
STM publisher name	
Portion	Excerpt (up to 400 words)
Number of excerpts	1
Author of this Wolters Kluwer article	No
Title of your thesis / dissertation	Improving the Debriefing Process in the Operating Room
Expected completion date	May 2019
Estimated size(pages)	40
Requestor Location	Rita Thompson 275 E. Green St. #1351 PASADENA, CA 91101 United States Attn: Rita Thompson
Publisher Tax ID	13-2932696
Billing Type	Invoice
Billing Address	Rita Thompson 275 E. Green St. #1351

PASADENA, CA 91101
United States
Attn: Rita Thompson
0.00 USD

Total

APPENDIX G

ORGANIZATIONAL READINESS FOR INTENT TO CHANGE PERMISSION TO USE

Consent to Use ORIC

Inbox

Rita Thompson <ritat@csu.fullerton.edu>

Tue, May 22,
2018, 4:20
PM

to chris_shea

Hello Dr. Shea, I am requesting to use and modify your ORIC in a project that will help me meet requirements for my Doctor of Nursing Practice program. Please let me know if you have any questions. Thank you for your consideration.

Shea, Christopher Michael Chris_Shea@unc.edu via admin@unc.onmicros

Wed, May 23,
2018, 6:55 AM

to me

Hello Rita,

I'm happy to hear about your interest in using the ORIC. You are welcome to use it. We just ask that you cite the Shea et al. 2014 article as the source of the items in your survey and in any reports or publications you develop.

Attached is the 10-item version, which includes the items that performed best in our assessment, as reported in the 2014 paper. We have received some feedback that using all 5 "change commitment" items may be unnecessarily repetitive. This may be true, although I suggest using at least 3 of them. My least favorite is the "whatever it takes" item because of its connotation.

Hope this helps.

All the best,
Chris

Christopher M. Shea, PhD, MA, MPA
Assistant Professor, Health Policy and Management
Faculty Lead, NC TraCS Dissemination & Implementation Science Methods
Unit
Research Fellow, Cecil G. Sheps Center for Health Services Research
Department of Health Policy and Management

McGavran-Greenberg Hall 1104F, CB # 7411
UNC Gillings School of Global Public Health
The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Chapel Hill, NC 27599-7411
Phone: 919-966-1938
www.sph.unc.edu/hpm

The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Chapel Hill, NC 27599-7411
Phone: 919-966-1938
www.sph.unc.edu/hpm

APPENDIX H

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Purpose (Author, year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results/Findings	Author, Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Evaluate overall adherence to use of DBC Bartz-Kurycki et al., 2017	Prospective, observational Standardized form to assess completion of 8 prespecified checkpoints in DB	603 observed cases over 3 years (3, 8-week periods) with 11 student observers/Pediatric surgical services in 234 bed academic children's hospital, 14 subspecialties	Standardized form to assess completion of 8 prespecified checkpoints in DB Checkpoint completed if verbally stated and discussed Pearson chi-square test to evaluate adherence to each checkpoint	Overall DB 92% (90.6%, 90.3%, 94.9%) p = 0.14 Completed in full 55%, 48%, 50% 3 ↓ scoring checkpoints with ↓ over 3 years: post-op plan discussion (p < 0.001), correct counts (p = 0.047), & ID & labeling of specimens (minimal diff) Improvement: intra-op concerns (p < 0.001) & blood loss (p = 0.00) DB compliance ↑ from 51 % to 81 %, then 82 % - 91 %	Complete compliance DBC much lower with minimal improvement Benefits of DB need to be promoted to enhance adherence Better understanding of barriers along with meaningful use needed to target interventions to improve buy-in & communication
Improving the culture of safety in the OR by improving DB compliance Hypothesis – DB will improve communication with all team members & enhance culture of safety Magill et al., 2017.	Quality improvement incentive project (financial incentive offered to residents if goals met) IV- Improved DB compliance; > 80 % vs. low DB compliance DV-Improved culture of safety	UCSF neurosurgery team/UCSF neurosurgery OR	DB advisory group to implement & recommend Pre/post 10 question, safety culture survey DB compliance- paper audit cards, 2014 web-based audits, 2015	Survey questions: Encouraged to report safety concerns MDs & RNs work as a team Important issues communicated Patient safety is priority – all p < 0.05 Fidelity improvement: Briefings occur regularly (p < 0.001)	DB can be a tool to ↑ culture of safety & attitudes of safety ↑ survey scores in teams that use DB Also, ↑ identification & reporting of issues

Purpose (Author, year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results/Findings	Author, Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Review of literature re: DB, in OR & reporting of experience with invention & implementation of DB pilot Zuckerman et al., (2012)	Quality improvement project & observational study Lean 5S IV – implementation of DB DV - ↑ Patient safety	Perioperative staff /Vanderbilt University Hospital neurosurgery	“Just in time training” to pilot team for DBC implementation & test of knowledge Post implementation team meeting to provide feedback & suggestions for improvement	Successful design of DB tool does not equal successful implementation Potential barriers: 1) Surgeon buy in 2) Surgeon case exit 3) Administrative infrastructure to use obtained data to guide practice change 4) Need for electronic integration	Poor DBC compliance is multifactorial & most likely due to existing culture of individual practice & expertise No data on reduction of ↓ morbidity ↓ error rates & ↑ communication
Improvements in CL compliance require committed interdisciplinary strategy Putnam et al., (2014)	Observational study over 2 yrs. 2 sets of interventions IV – multifaceted, interdisciplinary team strategy DV - improvements in checklist adherence	873 cases/240 bed academic children’s hospital	3 independent observational periods to assess delivery of CL Pre/Post survey Convenience sample Student observers measured rate of compliance in 14 checkpoints	Adherence to CL ↑ after each period, 30 %, 76 %, 96 % (p < 0.001) Compliance of all 14 checkpoints ↑ from 0 %, 19, %, 61 % (p < 0.05) Surveys showed overall ↑ post interventions Interventions aimed at culture, engagement, & comprehension ↑ adherence 30 % to 96 % Protocols & guidelines were not successful	Nurse led CL initiation along with standardization resulted in improved adherence & consistency Limitations: no data regarding morbidity or mortality Hawthorne effect may produce bias CL developed by local stakeholders & may not be appropriate for all users Uncontrolled before & after study

Purpose (Author, year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results/Findings	Author, Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				Implementation strategies influence success	
Multi-level effects of standardized CRM training & specific system improvement projects in a pediatric surgery department Salvage et al., (2017)	Multi-level prospective single case study SQUIRE – guidelines for eval. of QI efforts	All physicians and staff/Pediatric surgery unit at a children’s hospital in Sweden 5500 surgeries annually	Data collected in 4 areas: -Relevance of CRM, standardized, written course eval -Safety culture, Pre/post Patient Safety Culture survey -Team behaviors, SSC measured by collection of CL, MedPACT observations -Effects on periop care, EMR data collection over 3 yr.	Overall DB 92% (90.6%, 90.3%, 94.9%) p = 0.14 Completed in full 55%, 48%, 50% 3 ↓ scoring checkpoints with ↓ over 3 years: post-op plan discussion (p < 0.001), correct counts (p = 0.047), & ID & labeling of specimens (minimal diff) Improvement: intra-op concerns (p < 0.001) & blood loss (p = 0.00 DB compliance ↑ from 51 % to 81 %, then 82 % - 91 %	NTS, use of tools ↑ Adherence to new practices persisted over 5 yr study duration Implementation of SSC worked as a catalyst for change CRM, safety tools ↑NTS, outcomes, & safety culture
How use of HO tool & standardized process can improve patient safety by increasing the effectiveness of periop communication Robinson (2016)	QI, team-based pilot project IV: HO communication tool (PEARLS) & standardized process DV: improved communication of critical elements of care in the immediate postop period and standardization of HO	Periop department of an acute care community hospital in a suburb of a large metropolitan area 8 ORs & 12 PACU beds All periop RNs participation required No inclusion or exclusion criteria for postop patient population	Pre/post survey of knowledge & process (4-point Likert) 1-month pre/post implementation HO audits (direct observations of OR to PACU HO) Knowledge post-test to demonstrate	Statistically significant difference between HO observations/audits pre vs. post implementation (↑in postop HO scoring) Statically significant ↑ (no P values) in mean knowledge & process scores from pre - post implementation (paired t test)	“Standardized hand-off process & use of the PEARLS tool improved communication of essential/critical information and met regulatory HO communication standards” (Robinson, 2016, p. 253) Similar to 2009 John Hopkins study

Purpose (Author, year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results/Findings	Author, Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	communication among periop nursing staff Iowa Model of Evidence-Based practice framework & principles of Lean Six Sigma Development of hand- off tool, PEARLS Education & simulation	Multidisciplinary team (DNP student, OR nurse champion, PACU RN champion, CRNA champion, director of surgical services, OR & PACU supervisors, & Lean Six Sigma master black belt)	competence of HO regulations Development of a periop specific tool to measure outcomes of PEARLS HO effectiveness Data analysis using paired <i>t</i> test design	100% cognitive confidence on HO content post-	Major limitation = Focus on OR to PACU, should include entire periop environment (patient assessment, periop, inpatient RNs)
Association between TW and CL performance, how they relate, conditions that influence each Singer et al., (2016)	2 validated observation/ coaching tools, both 5- point scales TW SSC performance	207 surgical procedures between 4/11- 1/13/Surgical teams in 10 hospitals across South Carolina that perform surgery and implemented SSCs	TW among surgical team in OR, 5- domains-Clinical leadership, communication, coordination, respect, assertiveness SSC performance- processes of care, briefing, debriefing, buy-in, additional data	Relationship of TW to CL performance ($p < 0.05$) Surgeon buy-in = \uparrow CL item performance ($p < 0.0001$) Clinical leadership = \uparrow CL item performance ($p < 0.05$) Older patient = \uparrow CL item performance (10 yrs. older = 2 % - 3 % more items completed) Longer cases = \uparrow CL item performance ($p < 0.05$)	Performance of CL items linked to surgeon buy-in and TW Surgeon participation helps to eliminate hierarchy Sign-in performed more often than sign- out Could lead CL improvements Participating hospitals were volunteers Different observers Same source bias Hawthorne effect
Does implementation B/D	Qualitative Likert-type pre/post survey	Interdisciplinary adult and pediatric surgical	Pre-survey-Survey Monkey-Likert scale data, demographics,	B/D in 40 of 50 cases, pre- survey completed by 62 staff	B/D proves staff attitudes in the OR, creates safe, efficient,

Purpose (Author, year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results/Findings	Author, Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
change staff attitudes in the OR? Carbines (2017).	4 phases over 6 m IV-implementation of briefing & debriefing DV-improved staff attitudes	staff in 31 OR Auckland hospital	free writing section analyzed using comparative analysis Post used Buzz Channel due to tech. difficulties to analyze qualitative and quantitative data, same methods as pre Compare/contrast of each survey	vs. 41 post due to ineligibility Challenges identified 68 % noted improvements in case management, 84% adult staff reported improvements vs. 33 % pediatric staff Late starts & finish times ↑ with B/D	effective environment, identifies positive/negative outcomes
Coaching as an effective intervention to improve communication in OR. Are more briefings performed after coaching? Is there a difference in the quality of B/D after coaching? Kleiner, Link, Maynard, & Carpenter (2014).	Qualitative, Perioperative Patient Focused Model (conceptual model) Pre/post intervention observations Two-tailed comparison IV- B/D coaching DV- improved communication in OR	320 observations (120 pre, 120, post) SS department of an academic hospital, 17 IP & 8 OP ORs, 225 staff	CRM Observation Checklist used to rate quality of pre & post intervention B/D (5- point Likert scale) Independent t-tests to evaluate the quality of B/D	B/D occurred 100% of time pre-intervention (possible Hawthorne effect) Increase in briefings checklist scores: 3:478 to 3.644 ($p = .044$) & debriefing 2.377 to 2.991 (p < .0001)	Coaching was an effective intervention in improving the quality of communication

Note. Addtl = additional; Anest = anesthesiologist; B/D = briefings & debriefings; CL = checklist; CRM = Crew Resource Management; DV = dependent variable; HO = hand-off; IP = in-patient; IV = independent variable; M = month; NS = neurosurgery; OP = out-patient; OR = operating room; PO = post-operative; RN = registered nurse; SS = surgical services.